

SHAHSNING HAYOT QADRIYATLARI VA UNING TAYM MENEJMENTDAGI AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada qadriyatlar, umuminsoniy, ijtimoiy-axloqiy, madaniy-ma'naviy ahamiyatini ko'rsatish uchun qo'llanadigan tushunchalar, inson va insoniyat uchun ahamiyatli bo'lgan barcha narsalar, masalan, erkinlik, tinchlik, adolat, ijtimoiy tenglik, ma'rifat, haqiqat, yaxshilik, go'zallik, moddiy va ma'naviy boyliklar, an'ana, urf-odat va boshqa qadriyatlar haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar. Qadryat, fazilat, shaxning hayot qadriyatlari, qadryatning taym menejmentdagi o'rni

Аннотация. В статье используются понятия, отражающие ценности, общечеловеческую, социально-этическую, культурно-духовную значимость, все важные для человека и человечества вещи, например, свобода, мир, справедливость, социальное равенство, просвещение, истина, добро, красота, упоминаются материальные и духовные блага, традиции, обычаи и другие ценности.

Ключевые слова. Ценность, добродетель, ценности личной жизни, место ценности в тайм-менеджменте

Abstract. The article uses concepts that reflect universal, social-ethical, cultural-spiritual significance, all things important for humans and humanity, for example, freedom, peace, justice, social equality, enlightenment, truth, goodness, beauty, material and spiritual are mentioned benefits, traditions, customs and other values.

Key words. Value, virtue, personal life values, the place of value in time management

Value is a concept used to show the universal, social-ethical, cultural-spiritual importance of certain events in reality. All things that are important for a person and humanity, such as freedom, peace, justice, social equality, enlightenment, truth, goodness, beauty, material and spiritual wealth, tradition, customs, etc., are values. Therefore, everything that is valuable to a person is a value. Value is also divided into several groups within itself. These are national values, personal values and universal values. The values that represent the most

important aspects, laws and relationships of the world, nature and society have a universal character. Such values are eternal values that do not lose their importance. The value associated with the life, lifestyle, language, culture, spirituality, customs and traditions, past and future of a particular people, nation, people is called national value. Things, characteristics and qualities that belong only to a person are personal values. Therefore, value can belong to a whole society, a certain area and only one person. President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev states in his book "We will resolutely continue our path of national development and raise it to a new level" that "we need to mobilize all our strength and capabilities to educate our youth in the spirit of national and universal values." After all, national and universal values are a social phenomenon that has passed the test of life and serves the development of mankind. Nowruz holiday, which is an example of our national values, is solemnly celebrated in our country every year. Nowruz means a new day. That is, day and night are equal on this day. In Eastern countries, this day is celebrated as a new day, the first day of the new year. During Nowruz, our mothers cook sumacs in a pot, and our young ones prepare various dishes, blue somsa, norin, gilmindi, chuchvara and other spring salads. Our boys try their hand at our national games, such as wrestling, tug-of-war, chillak and kopkari. The girls put on new dresses, comb their hair, and sing songs. It is no exaggeration to say that Navruz is one of the indelible and eternal values of our nation. Our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev describes Navruz in his address to our people: "Navroz is a truly national holiday, a reflection of our national identity, an integral part of our spiritual and cultural life. Indeed, our strength is in unity and harmony; our strength is in kindness, mutual support and generosity; our success lies in our high confidence in the future." Today, one of the important tasks facing the educational process is the use of our national values and traditions in the education of a well-rounded person.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: "Uzbekistan has always been faithful to its traditions in the field of inter-ethnic harmony and religious tolerance, and has never deviated from this path." goes ahead without work. Today, we believe in our multi-ethnic people, our youth, who are our hope and support, and we are reaching the finish line. Thinking about the happiness of our dear children and grandchildren, we are setting ourselves huge tasks in view of the bright future of our country and people. It is appropriate to quote the following sentences: "A people with a great intention will have a great work, a bright life and a prosperous future". Mothers are of great importance and they act as the most effective weapon in the process of

education. The future of our country is in the hands of our youth. What kind of youth? Physically healthy, mentally mature, well-rounded youth. Such young people need education and morals. , respects national values and traditions and preserves them. As long as Uzbekistan has its great history, culture and spirituality, its future will be great. In conclusion, we can say that our tomorrow, our future , the development of our society depends on the level of education we give to our youth today. The issue of raising a generation that is in tune with the world news, able to analyze current situations, and has its own firm point of view is considered an important and undeniable issue facing our entire nation and state. The wisdom of our ancestors that knowledge acquired in youth is like a pattern carved on stone shows that respect for national and universal values should be instilled in the human heart from a young age. Each of us realizes that we want to be happy and fulfilled in life at certain stages of our life. We have our own ideas about our happiness and understand that we want to be happy! However, we live in a world where we have to get up and do something every day... Day after day... Not just doing routine things, but knowing what we are doing! We must be clear about what we want to achieve; and most importantly - how to do it. Unfortunately, we sometimes get so used to doing the same thing that we forget why we're doing it. We just don't have time to stop and look around - the joy of life! We live in a world of temptation. Every second we make a choice. In order not to doubt, you must first make the right decision. It's time to decide what's important and what's second to none. And is it possible to lose something and everything from his life, because it does not make sense? These are vital values. We are in order. When we see a clear vision of reality, our future, our ideal world, we start to try to make ourselves better, we try to live a better life... But if we don't know how to define life values, our efforts will be in vain. Recognize yourself and understand what is important. For parents and people who have been around us since childhood, we have an idea about it. He walked confidently in life, understood what was important to him and compiled a list of life values. Second, it is probably still being resolved, they don't know what to do. Today, the more regretful the choice of a healthy lifestyle and short-term pleasures, the more temptations are given priority. We first spend money to make our health worse, then we rebuild it!

The science of values - Axiology (aksio means value, logos means science, teaching) is a field of philosophy that studies and deals with this issue. During the time of the former Union, there was very little information in this regard. Due to independence, our views on values changed rapidly. The glorified party-

class values of the former Union have turned into a mirage, unable to meet the requirements of modern realities, and closed together with the pages of history from the past decades. In Uzbekistan, attention to values has increased, its various aspects are being analyzed by scientists and specialists. Many topics of the philosophy of values - axiology occupy a special place in the scientific research of our specialists. Similarly, "What is value?" before answering the question, it is necessary to study the history of the subject, albeit a short one. Without it, the importance of values today and in the future cannot be understood. The history of the subject of values, its roots, and the formation of principles of human appreciation have a long history. In this regard, Western scientists mainly rely on the European cultural heritage and ideas, and mention the names of many scholars. The formation of the science of axiology (aksio - value, logos - teaching) in the West, which deals with values, is a certain basis for their views. We do not doubt that this topic, which Socrates and Plato, Aristotle and Hegel paid great attention to, has its own history in Western philosophy. But this topic is not alien to the ancient and modern East, especially Uzbekistan! Searching for its deepest aspects not only from the West, but also from the East is probably not without benefits. There are traces of this theme in the works of thinkers such as Khorezmi, Farabi, al-Bukhari, al-Tirmizi, Beruni, Ibn Sina, Najmuddin Kubra, Yassavi, Naqshband, Ulug'bek, Navoi, Mashrab, Bedil, Behbudi, Avloni, whose names are forever etched in the history of our civilization. , deep edges are opened. It is a matter of finding these traces, not forgetting them, polishing them, and interpreting them objectively from the point of view of contemporary realities. The history of the evaluation criteria created by our generations and ancestors goes back to the oldest tales, legends, stories, epics, i.e. examples of folk oral creativity. In the works about Spitamen, Muqanna and Jalaluddin Manguberdi, legends and epics about Alpomish, To'maris and Shiroq, many universal values such as patriotism, sacrifice for the freedom of the people and the country are described. A bright example of our spiritual heritage - "Avesta" is the sacred book of Zoroastrianism, in which the value system of this religion, the criteria of appreciation, the national ideas of that time are vividly expressed. is important. During this period, the Arab invasion was carried out, and Islam became the dominant religion. It should be recognized that the issues of divine value and appreciation described in the Qur'an and Hadiths have influenced the history and culture of our people. At the same time, it should be noted that many of our national values were lost during the Arab invasion. That's right Unfortunately, the period of prosperity in the

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Middle Ages, which created the highest standards of appreciation characteristic of our civilization, gradually declined after the reign of the Timurids, and the centralized state disintegrated. First Khiva Khanate and Bukhara Emirate, then Kokan Khanate came into existence. This process, which spanned more than three hundred years, went through wars between khanates, emirates, different dynasties, and ethnic groups, and incessant conflicts. By the middle of the 19th century, despite the fact that it was divided into emirates and khanates, Turkestan, which lived independently, was invaded by Tsarist Russia, and our country became a colony of the empire. The values and values of the colonialists were forcibly instilled among our people. At the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, a stream of "jadids" appeared in our country. If you pay attention to the heritage of M. Behbudi, Sofizoda, Avloni, Cholpon, Fitrat and other modernists, you can see how wide the scope of spiritual concepts was in our country at that time, how rich the philosophical language is, how well it is compatible with literature. can be clearly seen. In their works, we sometimes come across values and concepts that we have already forgotten from our memory, our language, and even our language. The legacy of the Jadids could have a greater impact on the culture of our people. Unfortunately, the political processes started by the Bolsheviks took away the rich heritage of this generation, its fate was sad, it was banned. The consequences of one hundred and thirty years of attempts to turn the eastern standards of appreciation, which were honored by the past generations and inherited from our great ancestors, into a mirage, are still felt. Only by the years of independence, positive changes began in this area.

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